

FORMATION OF STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN THE PROCESS OF EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Competence characterizes a person's experienced possession of the relevant competence, including his personal attitude to it and the subject of activity. In fact, competence is some alienated, predetermined requirement (norm) for the student's educational preparation, and competence is his personal quality (a set of qualities) that has already taken place and minimal experience in relation to activities in a given field. Competence is always personally colored by the qualities of a particular student.

Keywords. *Communicative culture, skills and abilities, communicative competence, socio-psychological interaction, self-education, personality-oriented*

The formation of a new type of society requires a new methodological basis for the entire education system, an understanding of the role of teachers and students in a new context, and the construction of the educational process as a personality-oriented one. At the same time, it is assumed that the positions of participants in the educational process will change. In these conditions, the success of solving educational problems largely depends on the communicative culture of the teacher and students. The teacher now acts as an organizer of independent cognitive activity of students, which is aimed at the formation of key competencies, and the student strives for self-education in the course of communicative interaction with the teacher.

Personality-oriented learning is aimed at developing all components of a student's competence. According to the works of A.V. Khutorsky, the individual competence of the student includes interpersonal communication and all types of communication. Individual competence is knowledge of factual material, possession of the skills and abilities of educational activities and the experience that the student has acquired in various fields of activity. In the formation of competence, experience

outstrips the acquisition of new knowledge. Learning by experience creates competence [Khutorskoy, A.V. 2003:60].

Among the key competencies of students, I would like to highlight the communicative competence as the main element of the communicative culture. It is through communicative competence that the communicative culture of students is realized.

Competence in communication presupposes the willingness and ability to build a dialogue, so necessary for a person in all spheres of life.

Communicative competence is the ability to establish and maintain the necessary contacts with other people. Competence includes a set of knowledge, skills and abilities that ensure effective communication. Communicative competence involves the ability to change the depth and circle of communication, to understand and be understood by communication partners. In general, communicative competence is a system of internal resources necessary to build effective communication in a certain range of situations of personal interaction [Rubtsova, A.2019, 497]. In general, competence in communication is usually associated with mastering not any one position as the best, but with an adequate introduction to their spectrum. Flexibility in an adequate change of psychological positions is one of the essential indicators of competent communication.

Communication in pedagogical activity is a means of solving educational tasks; socio-psychological support of the educational process; a way of organizing the relationship between the teacher and the trainees, which determines the success of training and upbringing.

From the point of view of A. N. Leontiev, communication should be considered as a certain side of activity, because communication acts as an element of any activity. In this case, activity is a necessary condition for communication [Leontiev A. A. 1997:365].

V. A. Kan-Kalik defines professional and pedagogical communication as a system of organic socio-psychological interaction between a teacher and students, the content of which is the exchange of information, the organization of relationships using communicative means.

Communication, according to V. A. Kan-Kalik, acts as:

- a means of solving educational problems;
- socio-psychological support of the educational process;

●a way of organizing the relationship between the teacher and students. [Kan-Kalik V.A. 1987:190]

Various learning technologies should stimulate the learner's ability to think, independently solve cognitive and practical tasks. They allow not only to optimize the learning process, but also to build models with which you can demonstrate various training options and select the most effective ones among them. Focusing on the interaction of participants in the educational process, we will consider effective forms of such interaction, among which we include communicative learning technologies.[Rubtsova, A.2019, 497]

S.V. Mitrokhina defines communicative learning technology as a personality-oriented technology based on the joint activity of participants in the educational process, during which, on the basis of a cognitive dialogue motivated by internal needs, a common view is developed on ways to solve the task, and this process is aimed at achieving the planned results [Mitrokhina S.V.2013].

Communication technologies are precisely technologies, because they give a greater share of probability in achieving the planned result. This is not a random, but a systematic process aimed at an unconditional impact on the audience.

Research by psychologists has shown that only 30% of students are actively involved in the educational and cognitive process. Therefore, it is not enough to organize communication between its participants in the learning process, it is necessary to create a special space for the interaction of subjects of educational activity, in which each student is actively involved in the collective search for truth. Statements, arguing his point of view, respectfully defending his position in the dialogue, formulating a mutually acceptable point of view, the student acquires communicative competence, successfully formed with the help of communicative learning technologies. The establishment of communication links between participants in the educational process is an important component of developmental learning.

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